
336.71:368.1

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THE INSURANCE SYSTEM OF RUSSIA: A SYSTEMIC ANALYSIS OF PROBLEMS AND A MODEL FOR IMPROVEMENT

The article presents a comprehensive study of the insurance system of the Russian Federation as a key institution within the state's financial system. The relevance of the topic is determined by the need to identify the main problems of the insurance sector, ensure the stability of the financial sector, and improve the efficiency of its operational mechanisms. In the context of accelerated digitalization, the impact of sanctions, increasing systemic risks, and the need for innovative development of the insurance market, there is a clear necessity for a comprehensive analysis of the structure, functions, and characteristics of the insurance system.

The study employs methods of analytical and comparative-theoretical analysis, a systemic approach, classification, modeling, and synthesis. This methodological framework allowed for examining the theoretical foundations of the insurance system, identifying the interconnections among its elements, functions, and characteristics, as well as classifying insurance systems according to key criteria.

Special attention is given to the structural components of the insurance system, its elements and functions, systemic characteristics, and classification types. A systemic analysis of problems in the insurance sector was carried out at three levels: elements, functions, and characteristics, identifying the main constraints and deficiencies affecting the system's efficiency.

Based on this analysis, an authorial model of systemic analysis of the insurance system's problems and pathways for their resolution was developed. The model allows for identifying critical issues, determining directions for improvement, and serves as a theoretical basis for developing measures to enhance the resilience of the insurance sector.

The results demonstrate that the systemic approach to studying the insurance system provides a comprehensive understanding of its condition, facilitates the identification of internal and external factors affecting operational efficiency, and enables the development of measures to improve its performance. The proposed model can be applied as a tool for scientific analysis and practical enhancement of the insurance sector, thereby increasing its significance for the financial stability and economic development of the Russian Federation.

Keywords: financial system, insurance system, elements of the insurance system, functions, characteristics, classification, systemic analysis, improvement model.

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2. : : 7000
3. / [.].— ,2007.— 814 .
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4. » ,2004.— 1008 .
5. / ; ;—
6. ,1999.— 1056 .
7. ; , —5- .—
8. ,1998.— 823 .
9. : ,1998.— 480 .
10. - / , « » ,
- 2021.— 1168 .
11. [.] / [.] ; ,
12. ;
13. « » (. -) , -
14. , — : - ,2012.— 168 .
15. / — - ,2017.— 352 c.
16. , : : / —1.—
17. ,2021.— 716 .
18. , : / ;
19. , — : ,1978.— 495 .
20. : ,2000.— 896 .
21. : / ; ,
22. — : ,2001.— 509 .
23. ; [. ,] .—7- .— [.] : /
- 2013.— 875 .
24. : [2] /
25. : « » ,1994. .1: : 21.— 325 .
26. ; [.] / [.] : ,2005 (
27.) .— 575 .
28. / — : ,2015.— 356 .
29. : ,2022.— 120 .
30. : [.] /—
31. ,1999.— 799 .
32. : [.] / — [.] : ,2007.— 584 .
33. / / / / / / / : / , ;
34. ; - — : ,2010.— 200 .
35.— ,2004.— 889 .
36. : « » ,2009.— 380 .
37.
38. / //2016.— .1(47).— .2.— .379-383.
39. : / , , ;
40. ; [.] ; - — : -
41. - ,2020.— 324 .

26. : 27.11.1992
4015-1. — URL: www.consultant.ru/document/cons_doc_LAW_1307/ (: 10.10.2025).

SPISOK LITERATURY

1. Agoshkov, Ye. B., Evolyutsiya ponyatiya sistemy / Ye. B. Agoshkov, B. V. Akhlibinskiy // Voprosy filosofii. 1998. — 7. — S. 170–179.
2. Bol'shaya ekonomicheskaya entsiklopediya: BEE: samoye polnoye sovremennoye izdaniye: boleye 7000 ekonomicheskikh terminov i ponyatiy / [T. P. Varlamova i dr.]. — Moskva: Eksmo, 2007. — 814 s.
3. Bol'shaya rossiyskaya entsiklopediya. Rossiya / Kol. avt.; Otv. red. S. L. Kravets. — M.: Nauchnoye izd-vo «Bol'shaya rossiyskaya entsiklopediya», 2004. — 1008 s.
4. Ekonomicheskaya entsiklopediya / RAN, In-t ekonomiki; gl. red. L. I. Abalkin; zam. gl. red. F. I. Shamkhalov. — M.: Ekonomika, 1999. — 1056 s.
5. Brighkem, Yu. F. Entsiklopediya finansovogo menedzhmenta: Sokr. per. s angl. / Brighkem Yudzhin F.; obshch. red. vstupit. st. B. Ye. Pen'kova, V. V. Voronova; Redkol.: A. M. Yemel'yanov, V. V. Voronov i dr. — 5-ye izd. — M.: RAGS-Ekonomika, 1998. — 823 s.
6. Blank, I. A. Slovar'-spravochnik finansovogo menedzhera. Kiyev: Nika-tsentr, 1998. — 480 s.
7. Slovar' finansovo-ekonomicheskikh terminov / A. V. Sharkova, A. A. Kilyachkov, Ye. V. Markina i dr.; pod obshch. red. d. e. n., prof. M. A. Eskindarova. — 4-ye izd. — M.: Izdatel'sko-torgovaya korporatsiya «Dashkov i K», 2021. — 1168 s.
8. Slovar' finansovo-ekonomicheskikh terminov [Tekst] / [I. F. Drachinskaya i dr.]; pod red. I. Z. Yaryginoy, N. G. Kondrakhinoy; Federal'noye gos. byudzhethnoye obrazovatel'noye uchrezhdeniye vyssh. prof. obrazovaniya «Finansovyy un-t pri Pravitel'stve Rossiyskoy Federatsii» (Finansovyy un-t), Kaf. mezhdunar. valyutno-kreditnykh i finansovykh otnosheniy, Kaf. angliyskogo yaz. — Moskva: Finansovyy un-t, 2012. — 168 s.
9. Rayzberg, B. A. Sovremennyy sotsioekonomicheskii slovar' / B. A. Rayzberg. — M.: Infra-M, 2017. — 352 c.
10. Pareto, Vil'fredo. Sotsialisticheskiye sistemy: per. s fr.: Monografiya / V. Pareto. — I. — Moskva: Izdatel'skiy Tsentr RIOR, 2021. — 716 s.
11. Keynes, Dzh. M. Obshchaya teoriya zanyatosti, protsenta i deneg: Per. s angl. / Dzh. M. Keynes; Obshch. red. i predisl. A. G. Mileyskovskogo, I. M. Osadchey. — Moskva: Progress, 1978. — 495 s.
12. Klassika ekonomicheskoy mysli: Sochineniya / V. Petti, A. Smit, D. Rikardo, Dzh. M. Keynes, M. Fridmen. — Moskva: EKSMO-Press, 2000. — 896 s.
13. Khol, R. Organizatsii: struktury, protsessy, rezul'taty / R. K. H. Khol; per. s angl. Ye. Nesterovoy, T. Printsevoy. — Sankt-Peterburg: Piter, 2001. — 509 s.
14. Mishkin, Frederik S. Ekonomicheskaya teoriya deneg, bankovskogo dela i finansovykh rynkov [Tekst] / Frederik S. Mishkin; [per. s angl. O. K. Ostrovskoy, A. A. Rybyanets]. — 7-ye izd. — Moskva [i dr.]: Vil'yams, 2013. — 875 s.
15. Matuk, Zh. Finansovyye sistemy Frantsii i drugikh stran: [V 2 t.: per. s fr.] / Zh. Matuk. pod obshch. red. L. P. Pavlovoy. M.: «Finstatinform», 1994. T. 1: Banki: v 2 kn. Kn. 1. — 325 s.
16. Finansy i kredit: ucheb. dlya studentov vuzov, obuchayushchikhsya po ekon. spetsial'nostyam / [Romanovskiy M. V. i dr.]; pod red. M. V. Romanovskogo i G. N. Beloglazovoy. — Moskva: Vyssh. obrazovaniye, 2005 (GUP IPK Ul'yan. Dom pečati). — 575 s.
17. Rodionova V. M. Finansy / V. M. Rodionova. — M.: Prior, 2015. — 356 s.
18. Finansovaya sistema Rossii i zarubezhnykh stran: uchebnoye posobiye dlya bakalavriata / pod red. G. F. Ruchkinoy. — Moskva: Prometey, 2022. — 120 s.
19. Van Khorn, Dzheyms K. Osnovy upravleniya finansami: [Per. s angl.] / Dzh. K. Van Khorn. — Moskva: Finansy i statistika, 1999. — 799 s.
20. Finansy: [perevod s angliyskogo] / Zvi Bodi, Robert K. Merton. — Moskva [i dr.]: Vil'yams, 2007. — 584 s.
21. Kuz'min, I. G. / Finansovaya sistema / RF: uchebnoye posobiye / I. G. Kuz'min, G. A. Boyko, A. S. Trostin; pod red. I. G. Kuz'mina; Yarosl. gos. un-t im. P. G. Demidova. — Yaroslavl': YarGU, 2010. — 200 s.
22. Gabbard R. Glen. Den'gi, finansovaya sistema i ekonomika Uchebnik, Per. s angl.; Nauk. red. per. M. Savluk, D. Olesnevich. — K.: KNEU, 2004. — 889 s.
23. Baranova V. G. Finansovyy mekhanizm funktsionirovaniya strakhovoy sistemy. Odessa: «VMV», 2009. — 380 s.
24. Pozdnyakova L. A. Sushchnost' i sodержaniye strakhovoy sistemy kak sotsial'no-ekonomicheskoy kategorii / L. A. Pozdnyakova // Nauchnyy vestnik Uzhgorodskogo universiteta. 2016. — Vyp. 1(47). — T. 2. — S. 379–383.
25. Natsional'naya strakhovaya sistema: uchebnik / Ye. G. Knyazeva, Ye. A. Razumovskaya, Ye. Yu. Polovnova, V. A. Shelyakin; [pod red. Ye. G. Knyazevoy]; M-vo nauki i vyssh. obrazovaniya RF. — Yekaterinburg: Izd-vo Ural. un-ta, 2020. — 324 s.
26. Ob organizatsii strakhovogo dela v Rossiyskoy Federatsii: Zakon Rossiyskoy Federatsii ot 27.11.1992 4015-1. — URL: www.consultant.ru/document/cons_doc_LAW_1307/ (data obrashcheniya: 10.10.2025).

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